

Aesthetic Education of Children in the Family

Abdullaeva Masuda

Professor, Namangan state university

Abdullaeva Nilufar, Abdullaev Dilmurod

teacher Namangan state university

Abstract: *In modern pedagogy and education of children, aesthetic education of preschoolers is of particular importance, designed to create all the prerequisites for the formation of a developed and harmonious personality. Without it, the child will not be able to appreciate the beautiful, get genuine pleasure from listening to classical music or contemplating a picture, and even more so will not be able to create something of his own. He will become spiritually poor, boring, will not be able to understand his emotions, because when touching the beautiful, something inside him will respond, but he will not be able to understand what exactly. That is why parents should include this most important aspect in their education tactics, without shifting all responsibility to the employees of the preschool educational institution - the role of the family in the formation of personality is very great. For children of different ages, a variety of methods can be used and a variety of means can be used.*

Keywords: *pedagogy, emotion, preschool, child, music, picture, family, upbringing, spiritual world.*

Introduction

Aesthetic feelings, sensitivity to beauty not only enrich a person's life, his spiritual world, but also organize and direct his behavior and actions. Therefore, an important task for parents is to develop in the child an aesthetic sensitivity to everything around him.

The child reaches for a bright toy, he expresses joy from communicating with nature. How often do we hear from a child enthusiastic exclamations: "Look, what a beautiful flower!", "Look, what a butterfly!" But often adults do not pay due attention to this.

Like all abilities, the ability to aesthetic sensitivity can be developed and nurtured. A child who is able to admire objects in the surrounding world will be able to approach them more carefully, will try not to damage them, not to break them. This forms a humanistic attitude to the natural world in the child. The worst thing in a person is indifference, apathy, lack of interest in objects and phenomena of the surrounding world.

Materials.

How can artistic and aesthetic abilities be cultivated in a child in the family? Of great importance is cultivating observation, the ability to see and examine. Observation enriches the child's knowledge and visual representations of an object. Both sides, cognitive and emotional, are closely interconnected. Therefore, developing a child's culture of vision, the ability to observe, to carefully examine objects and phenomena is an important aspect of educational work in the family. But in order to develop aesthetic perception in children, an adult must have the ability of aesthetic vision.

Any excursion with children to nature, walks in the city, to the park, to the embankment are of great importance for the child. It is necessary to pay attention to the features and beauty of individual buildings in the city, their differences, brightness and color. Admire the beauty of flowering trees, bushes, flowers.

Notice the changes that occur in nature: the color of the leaves changes depending on the season, migratory birds fly south and then return again, clouds and clouds in the sky have different colors and shapes. The ability to contemplate beauty, to enjoy it is very important for the development of children's creativity. There are always objects for observation in order to expand the child's understanding of the world, its variability and beauty: birds flying over a meadow, a fluffy bumblebee sitting on a flower, snowflakes smoothly falling to the ground, and fallen leaves driven by the wind.

Research and methods.

The child's figurative aesthetic perception is qualitatively enriched in those cases when an adult uses *epithets, figurative expressions, poetic lines*. The process of perception itself should be emotionally joyful, evoke in the child a positive attitude towards reality, a desire to enjoy beauty, and depict what he saw.

Drawing is of great importance for the development of the child's artistic and aesthetic abilities. From the very beginning, a healthy approach to the child's visual activity in the family is important. The child's artistic abilities should not be exaggerated, saying in front of him that he is a future artist, but his creativity should not be treated carelessly, as unnecessary pampering.

When drawing, a child not only depicts certain objects or phenomena of the surrounding life, but also expresses his attitude to what is depicted by means within his capabilities. Therefore, the process of drawing in a child is connected with the evaluation of what he depicts, and in this evaluation the child's feelings, including aesthetic ones, always play a major role. In an effort to convey this attitude, the child seeks means of expression, mastering pencils and paints.

The most important thing is to notice the child's craving for creativity in time and support it. A figurative, well-chosen word of an adult is of great importance in the development of children's aesthetic sensitivity. It helps children understand what qualities, properties of an object can be attributed to its positive aesthetic assessment, that is, make it beautiful. Beautiful is what is simple, carefully and lovingly executed, what is truthful, colorful, subtle and elegant in form, pleasant in color combinations.

The development of a child's living aesthetic sensitivity to the surrounding world and the necessary assistance in his/her artistic activity, all kinds of encouragement and, finally, a well-thought-out organization of the child's communication with art - all this is available to parents. And this will be a solid foundation for the further artistic and aesthetic development of the child's developing personality.

From early childhood, children have a certain craving for beauty, they are attracted by brightly decorated toys, shiny and colorful objects. Little ones get real pleasure from listening to music or poems, fairy tales that their mother reads to them. These impulses, still unconscious, gradually become conscious, but only if parents help the baby to form a harmonious taste, creative and artistic abilities, aesthetic ideas. Only in this way can we achieve that the child's personality will be developed, and he himself - happy.

Results.

In preschool educational institutions, work on cultivating a desire for beauty is also of colossal importance. For this, the necessary conditions must be created, certain forms of classes must be conducted - making crafts, drawing, modeling, listening to classical works of art accessible to children and talking about what they have heard. Therefore, aesthetic education of preschoolers is a task that simultaneously faces parents and educators.

Toys should be beautifully arranged in the room, interesting reproductions should be hung, and cleanliness and order should be maintained. Flowering plants placed in a harmonious composition and a decorated aquarium with fish will also help achieve the set goal. All decorative elements should be combined with each other, forming a single ensemble.

For children of preschool age, you can choose a picture with an image of an animal, a familiar fairy-tale character, a "delicious" still life. Older kids will like a landscape, so it is better to use reproductions of Savrasov, Serov, Shishkin, Levitan. To keep the child interested, the pictures should be changed periodically, while telling the child information about the work itself and its author.

In addition, the nursery can be decorated with folk craft items, Dymkovo toys, and Khokhloma-style crafts. Of course, you shouldn't put expensive collectibles on the table of a young prankster, but something inexpensive made of ceramics can be a worthy decoration.

Parents need to instill in their children from an early age that trees and flowers, sunset and sunrise, clouds in the sky and waves in the river are beautiful, and they need to be taught to enjoy this beauty. To do this, they should introduce children to works about nature that are accessible to them, spend time outdoors, talk, answer questions, and set an example.

There are many things that can be used for aesthetic education of children. Thus, in any city there are beautiful streets, architectural buildings, museums, exhibitions are held. Preschoolers will be happy to learn something new, visiting such places. Walking around the city, you can introduce the child to the main attractions, paying attention to their sophistication, harmony.

Discussion.

If there are no museums in the city, reproductions and virtual tours, which can be viewed online, will help introduce the baby to works of art. It is necessary to turn on outstanding musical works for the little ones, talk about what they have heard, find out what thoughts and emotions the music of Beethoven or Mozart, Tchaikovsky and Rachmaninov evoked.

And, of course, we shouldn't forget about literary works. Preschoolers can understand Pushkin's fairy tales, especially if they look at high-quality color illustrations. They should also be introduced to the poems of Marshak, Barto, and the stories of Prishvin and Zhidkov.

It is important for parents to remember that not every child will become an artist or musician, but everyone should be able to feel the beautiful and get special pleasure from it. Therefore, you should not just ask your child to draw something or make a craft or applique, but also pay attention to already created objects of spiritual value.

When carrying out the tasks of aesthetic education of children, it is necessary to introduce them to the benefits of work, to tell them that there are a large number of professions, each of which is important.

Conclusion.

The most effective method is considered to be the first, personal example, including both appearance and behavioral features, moral principles. Looking at parents and educators who understand the beautiful, enjoy contemplating it, the child himself will want to become the same. Only in this way can one form an ideal, which will later form the basis of the artistic consciousness of the child.

Even the simplest aesthetic judgments that a child hears from adults have a great influence on him. If a child hears that something or other is beautiful because, although it is very simple in form, it is carefully and lovingly made, it is pleasant to hold in your hands, it is convenient to use, then the child gradually begins to understand that not only what is bright and elegant is beautiful, but also what is appropriate, masterfully made, harmonious in color and form.

In conclusion, I would like to say that I would very much like our children to grow up as aesthetically developed people who are able to perceive the beauty of the surrounding nature, capable of looking tenderly at children, animals, loving art, seeing beauty in everyday life. Such people perceive life incomparably richer, fuller, more joyfully.

Literatures:

1. Barysheva T. A. Creativity. Diagnostics and development. Monograph. St. Petersburg, 2002
2. Zhdanova S. N. Pedagogy of aesthetic mastering of the world: monograph. Orenburg, 2006. Ilyin E. P. Psychology of creativity, creativity, giftedness. St. Petersburg, 2012.
3. Pedagogy of aesthetic environment: theory and experience. Collection of scientific papers. Minsk, 2002.
4. Reprintsev A. V. Aesthetic attitude of personality to reality: Essence, structure, formation. Kursk, 2000.
5. Aesthetic worldview of children of different age groups: Collection of scientific articles. Moscow, 2007.
6. Yasvin V. A. Educational environment: from modeling to design. M., 2001
7. Shcherbakova T. N. The influence of the aesthetics of the educational environment on the development of creative abilities of students [Text] // Actual tasks of pedagogy: materials of the III Int. scientific conf. (Chita, February 2013). - Chita: Publishing House Young scientist, 2013.
8. Shcherbakova, E. V. Aesthetic education of children in the family from the standpoint of history and modernity / E. V. Shcherbakova, T. N. Shcherbakova. - Text: direct // Theory and practice of education in the modern world: materials of the X Int. scientific conf. (Chita, April 2018). - Chita: Publishing house Young scientist, 2018. - P. 49-54. - URL: <https://moluch.ru/conf/ped/archive/277/13979/>